

NEP 2020 ON EDUCATION FOR ALL INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND EQUABILITY

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Abstract

Education is the single greatest tool for achieving equality Social justice and opportunity. In constitution of India also Mentioned that provide Equal educational opportunities to all the citizens of country is the duty and responsibility and duty of government. Keep in Consideration right from independence many policies, acts, programs and many initiation taken place for Inclusive Education or CWSN. In NEP 2020 third Indian educational policy chapter 6 mentioned Equitable and Inclusive Education, Learning for all for holistic productive approach. Everyone equal by opinion by equal by opportunities Inclusive education, more than mainstreaming the learners with special needs, is also concerned with identifying and overcoming all barriers for effective, continuous and quality participation of all in education (Ramchand and Dummugudem,2014; Ahmad, 2015a), and providing a 'least restrictive environment' (LRE) to satisfactorily afford children with disabilities a meaningful educational benefit, together with others, in an accessible physical and human environment (ICF, 2001; Gal et al., 2010). Overtime, there has been a considerable shift in the understanding of 'disability', from the earlier medical interpretations of seeing 'disability' as a 'deficit' within the individual, to the concept of human rights and equitable opportunities for participation of all individuals (Wolery, 2000).. NEP 2020 is the first ominous policy replacing NEP 1986 it is a structural change in educational system ensuring equity and inclusion. Equity is all about flourishing fairly and equally with all concern. Inclusion is an acceptance and celebration of human diversity. It recognizes children with their special needs and believes incorporating them in to the main stream education system. NEP 2020 ensures that Community participation eliminating language barriers, gender equality and inclusion especially for early child care education by introducing gender inclusive funds. Inclusion of new pedagogical system. Inclusion of skill courses and inclusion of research. "Rather laughing on others lets laugh together, rather pulling legs lets pull hands because coming together is beginning keeping togetheris progress and working together is success."

Key words: Access, Equity, Quality, Opportunity, Affordability and Accountability.

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Introduction: Education plays an important role for the overall development of child and nation building. According to constitution of India providing equal educational opportunity and responsibility and duty of our country. Inclusive education is a new approach towards educating the children regardless with their abilities, disabilities (Physical and learning difficulties) and giftedness with that of normal ones within same roof It brings all students together in one classroom and community regardless of their strengths and weaknesses in any area. As seeks the maximum potential fall students. It is one of the most effective ways to promote inclusive and tolerant society. Keeping in consideration learning needs of differently abled children Indian Government had took Comprehensive Efforts over the last five decade. Providing comprehensive range of services. Starting from independence many schemes, policies, acts, programs and initiations regarding education related to primary, secondary, higher education and Inclusive Education. These are different Programs, policies Indian Education Commission (Kothari Commission) (1966), 1974 Integrated education for disabled children, NEP 1968, NEP 1986 , The National Policy on Education, 1986 (NPE, 1986), and the Program of Action (1992) stresses the need for integrating children with special needs with other groups. The objective to be achieved as stated in the NPE, 1986 is "to integrate the physically and mentally handicapped with general community as equal partners, to prepare them for normal growth and to enable them to face life with courage and confidence" Integrated Education The concept of integrated education in India has emerged during the mid-1950s. It is based on the medical model of disability and it emphasizes placement of children with disabilities in mainstream schools. The major thrust is on attendance. IYD 1991 International year of disabled person ,NEP 1992 , United Nations World Conference 1994, National policy for person with disability 1995 & PWD 2006, RTE 10th April 2010, RPWD 2016, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Rastrya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan.

Objectives:

To highlight and overview the policy of the newly accepted Inclusive Education. (NEP 2020)

To identify the innovations in new national policy regarding Inclusive Education.

To discuss the merits of inclusive practices in policy of NEP.

To discuss about equity, quality and inclusive education under the effective implementation of NEP 2020 to realize its goal.

NEP 2020 a sign of countries changing focus on quality education. This policy is based up on the pillars of equity, equality, access, affordability and accountability. The NEP 2020 is the

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first new education policy to be introduced in India in the 21st century, the last having been implemented in 1986 which was modified once in 1992. Before that, the first Education policy was passed in 1986. According to the Government the NEP 2020 has been formulated after having considered nearly over 2 lakhs suggestions from 2.5 lakh gram panchayats, 6,600 blocks ULBs and districts. The main aim of this policy is producing engaged, productive and contributing citizens for building an equitable, inclusive and plural society. The NEP 2020 has conveyed the structural change in the Education system which ensures the global knowledge super power, equity and inclusion.

Equity and Inclusion: The aim of equity and inclusion is now at the heart of new NEP. In the fields of higher or school education, inclusion involves restructuring the whole system with the aim of ensuring the wide range of educational opportunities; this includes curriculum, pedagogy and recreational opportunities, etc.

Inclusion of community participation and involvement: NEP 2020 focuses on conscious awareness of roles and duties and inclusion of community participation and involvement which would minimize the exclusion of students on the basis of socio-economic status language and disability. This will motivate students to learn more about the diverse culture of India, its knowledge system and tradition and also to sensitize them on human values, empathy, tolerance, human rights, gender equality, inclusion, and equity which will develop respect for diversity.

Reform structure and curriculum: NEP 2020 focuses on flexible curriculum and 100% enrollment.

The NEP aims to reduce the curriculum content on its core essential focusing on key concept. Critical thinking, experiential based or analysis –based learning. The condition of the primary education at government schools, the dropout rates of girls has put the country on the back foot in education. But the new NEP has given more focus to school learning with a new way of coping multidisciplinary programs and focuses on the 21st-century skills in teaching, learning and assessment. Alternative and innovative education centres will led to multiple pathways of effective learning and widespread participation of students of different groups.

Gender equality and inclusion:

NEP aims to ensure equity and inclusion in and through education by addressing all forms of exclusion and marginalization, disparity, vulnerability and inequality in education access, participation, retention and completion and in learning outcomes. Gender equality and inclusion are vital in achieving these aims and leaving no one behind. Education needs a

greater focus on accessibility, equity and quality. Remarkable signs of progress have been noticed in the past few years in respect of female participation up to secondary level. Such progress could be because of Government's policies and programs run for girl child-like "Beti Bachao Beti Padhao", "Sukanya and Balika Samridhi Yojana" and many more. But girls' enrolment is lower than that of boys at upper secondary education. Gross Education Ratio during 2015-2016 stands only 23.4% against 25.4% for boys in higher education and the gap is visible at all the social categories. Now, NEP's biggest effort is to bring gender sensitivity as an integral part of curriculum and gender inclusion fund to be raised up to class 12 which covers all the socio-economically disadvantaged groups and also the transgender.

Inclusion of new Pedagogical system for Early Child Care Education Early Child Care Education:

(ECCE) is not available to most young children, particularly children from economically disadvantaged families. Inclusion of this system will help children of early age to attain optimal outcomes in the domains of physical and motor development, cognitive development, socio- emotional-ethical development, cultural/artistic development, and the development of communication and early language, literacy, and numeracy.

Inclusion of Skill Courses: Other focus has been given to make student learn life skill when they complete their schooling so that they can be self-reliant by then. By including contemporary subjects, vocational courses and extra curriculum activities from the school level will pull back students towards their schools. "Bal Bhavan" as a special daytime boarding school, will be established to support mechanisms tailored to suit their needs and vitalize students to participate in art-related, career-related, and play-related activities. It is beneficial to them for future life.

National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986: The objective of NPE 1986 stated that "to integrate the physically and mentally handicapped with general community as equal partners, to prepare them for normal and overall development with self-esteem. Special emphasis on the removal of disparities and to equalize educational opportunities.

The NEP 2020 policy is designed to avoid segregation and isolation of ethnic and linguistic minorities, those with disabilities and also those who face learning difficulties due to language barriers and are at the risk of educational exclusion. NEP 2020 has set the goal for all to be authoritative with the command of different languages at different levels of education. Innovation in instructional method, Building capacity among teachers, Multidisciplinary /cross , Multidisciplinary /cross disciplinary educators approach

disciplinary educators approach, Multidisciplinary /cross disciplinary educators approach, Choice of schooling, Special schooling, home based school, Child centered education, The societal challenges could be addressed only through high-quality interdisciplinary research across Curriculum according to learners need/choice, Teacher equipped for identifying the disabled children. Identification of learning disabilities. Celebrating plurality and diversity and uniqueness. Experiential learning.

NEP 2020, also include research capabilities and output across disciplines. Fields and the very best research in the world has occurred only in multidisciplinary settings. Last pioneering thing happened in India was Right to Education and was inserted in the Constitution under Article 45 A. The Indian Constitution says free and compulsory education for all children up to 6-14 yrs., but the promise of providing education to all is still an obscure goal till date. Education has never been the criteria of voting rights because any person literate or illiterate who completes 18 years can vote. As the cornerstone of all educational decisions, the ray of hope has come through the new

National Education Policy, 2020, which talks about sustainable human development and universal education learning with equity and learning outcomes with research oriented mindset. India has always placed education at the Centre of its development agenda and with bridging the gender, social, regional gaps with community participation it will raise the spirits towards equal opportunities to all ensuring equity in this policy. It is going to be the beautiful blend of both ancient and modern knowledge system which university not only inculcate you to acquire knowledge but also helps in integrating Indian culture and ethos.

Equitable and inclusive education learning for all education is the single greatest tool for achieving an inclusive and contribute to the nation the education system must aim to benefit to aim Indian's children so that no child loses any opportunity to learn and excel because of circumstances of birth or background. This Policy reaffirms that bridging the social category gaps in access, participation, and (earning outcomes in school education will (continue to be one of the major goals of education sector development programs.

Chapter 14 which discusses analogous and mentoring all such students through suitable counselling and mentoring programs ensure sensitization of faculty, students on gender identity issue and its inclusion in aspects of the HEI, including curricula, strictly enforce no-discrimination and anti- harassment rules, Develop Institutional Development Plans that contain specific plans for action on increasing Participation from SEDGs, including but not limited to the above items. Processes, geographical and language barriers, poor employability

potential of many higher education programs, and lack of appropriate student support mechanisms. Additional actions that are specific to higher education shall be adopted by all **Governments and HEIs** as follows.

Earmark suitable Government funds for the education of SEDGs.

Set clear targets for higher 64-ER for SEDGs.

Enhance gender balance in admissions to HEIs.

Enhance access by establishing more high-quality HEIs in aspirational districts and Special Education Zones containing larger numbers of SEDGs.

Develop and support of -quality HEIs that teach in local/Indian languages or bilingually. The dynamics and also many of the reasons for exclusion of SEDGs from the education system are common across school and higher education sectors. Therefore, the approach to equity and inclusion must be common across school and higher education. Furthermore, there must be continuity across the stages to ensure sustainable reform.

Thus, the policy initiatives required to meet the goals of equity and inclusion in higher education must be read in conjunction with those for school education.

There are certain facets of exclusion, which are particular to or substantially more intense in higher education.

These must be addressed specifically, and include lack of knowledge of higher education opportunities, economic opportunity cost of pursuing higher education, financial constraints, and admission, accessible and disabled-friendly

Develop bridge courses for students that come across with disadvantaged educational backgrounds.

Provide socio-emotional and academic support and mentoring for all such students through suitable counselling and mentoring programs

Ensure sensitization of faculty, counsellor, and students on gender-identity issue and its inclusion in all aspects of the higher education including curricula.

Strictly enforce all no discrimination and anti-harassment rules.

Develop Institutional Development Plans that contain specific plans for action on increasing participation from SEDs, including but not limited to the above items.

Equity and Inclusion in Higher Education Recommendation -For Governments and higher education NEP 2020-Equity and Inclusion in Higher Education- Equity and Inclusion in Higher Education Entry into quality higher education can open a vast array of possibilities that can lift both individuals as well as communities out of the cycles of disadvantage. For this

reason, making quality higher education opportunities available to all individuals must be among the highest priorities. This Policy envisions ensuring equitable access to quality education to all students, with a special emphasis on SEDGs. The dynamics and also many of the reasons -For exclusion of SEDGs -From the education system are common across school and higher education sectors. Special educator National Education Policy 2020-Education is - Fundamental for achieving - Pull human potential, developing an equitable and just society, and promoting national development. Providing universal access to quality education is the key to India's continued ascent, and leadership on the global stage in terms of economic growth, social justice and equality, scientific advancement, national integration, and cultural preservation. Universal high-quality education is the best way forward -For developing and maximizing our country's rich talents and resources - For the good of the individual, the society, the country, and the world. India will have the highest population of young people in the world over the next decade, and our ability to provide high- quality educational opportunities to them will determine the -Future of our country.

Make admissions processes more inclusive.

Make the curriculum more inclusive.

Increase employability potential of skill education programs.

Develop more degree courses taught in Indian languages and bilingually.

Ensure all buildings and -Facilities are wheelchair-accessible and disabled-friendly.

Develop bridge courses for students that come from disadvantaged educational backgrounds.

j) Provide socio-emotional and academic support and mentoring for all such students through suitable counselling and mentoring programs.

Ensure sensitization of faculty, counsellor, and students on gender-identity issues and its inclusion in all.

RECOMMENDATIONS SPECIAL EDUCATORS NEP 2020: Educational is the fundamental for achieving full human potential developing an equitable and justice society and promoting national development providing universal access quality to education is the key to India's continued ascent and leadership on the global stage in terms of economic growth for social justice and equality ,scientific advancement ,national integration and cultural preservations.Universal high quality and education is the best and maximizing our country rich Education sector development programs to be one of the major goals of all in Education will continue participation, and learning outcomes.

Innovation of NEP 2020:

Multidisciplinary Approach.

Vocational skilled Education.

Student centric.

Emphasis on quality education.

Elimination of Commercialization of education.

Equity research initiatives.

Global progress.

More equitable, affordable education.

Quality and Accessibility:

Introduced information communication technology. of Multilingual approach.

Boost on online methods.

Reforms in school structures and examinations and teacher management.

Experiential learning.

Flexible curriculum.

Assistive devices, technology based supportive tools.

Appropriate teaching –learning material.

Local Language offering.

Capacity building courses for teacher educators.

Critical Review and Reflection on draft of NEP -2020:

“Curriculum and pedagogy will be transformed by 2022 in order to minimize rote learning and instead encourage holistic development and 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, scientific temper, communication, collaboration, multilingualism, problem-solving, ethics, social responsibility, and digital literacy.” Introduction of Computers in the education system has been often termed as an important innovation. Technology though would have not contributed in changing the physical look of the classroom but has in many ways aided in redesigning education sector and its use though extensive should not be restrictive.

Conclusion: The draft of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 looks progressive with a clear objective of restructuring Indian educational system. The draft of National Education Policy finally looks like it has attained the level of competence. Equitable and Inclusive Education Learning for All NEP 2020-Education is the single greatest tool for achieving social justice and equality. Inclusive and equitable education - while indeed an essential goal in its own right - is also critical to achieving an inclusive and equitable society in which every citizen has the opportunity to dream, thrive, and contribute to the nation. The education

system must aim to benefit India's children so that no child loses any opportunity to learn and excel because of circumstances of birth or background. This Policy reaffirms that bridging the social category gaps in access, participation, and learning outcomes in school education will continue to be one of the major goals of all education sector development programs.

REFERENCES:

<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/voices/nep-2020-making-education>

more-inclusive/

<https://www.aicte-india.org/sites/default/files/nep2020.pdf>

https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf

<https://www.highereducationdigest.com/new-education-policy-a-few-important>

things-that-you-need-to-know-from-the-leaders-in-education/

<https://www.hindustantimes.com/education/nep-2020-implementation-of-new>

education-policy-in-our-education-system/story/bw4OiekFCamI7NPoNkgAoJ.html

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343769198_Analysis_of_the_Indian_National_Education_Policy_2020_towards_Achieving_its_Objectives

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343769198_Analysis_of_the_Indian_National_Education_Policy_2020_towards_Achieving_its_Objectives

<https://www.ukfiet.org/2020/examining-disability-inclusion-in-indias-new>

National-education

policy/#:~:text=India's%20National%20Education%20Policy%202020,exclusive%20of%20children%20with%20disabilities.

<https://www.ukfiet.org/2020/examining-disability-inclusion-in-indias-new> national-educationpolicy/#:~:text=India's%20National%20Education%20Policy%202020,exclusive%20of%20children%20with%20disabilities.

rsrr.in/2020/09/29/new-education-policy-inclusive-education India/

www.education.gov.in

www.mhrd.gov.in